

Paper: Can Users Trust Process Mining?

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Supporting Materials

In this document we provide additional materials to section **3. Research Method and Data Collection**

1. Participants Selection

Inclusion criteria

The goal of this paper (and interviews) is to gain better understanding on how business users of a process mining (PM) solutions trust the input data that was used for the process mining analysis development and the analysis itself as process mining output (for example, set of dashboards in process mining solution). Therefore, **as our main selection criteria we focused on:**

- 1) Participants from industry/practice with a **business user** roles in process mining.
- 2) Participants with a **consumer** role activities. In case users combined both roles responsibilities, we asked them to focus on the consumer point of view. However, when user had more producer activities, we decided to not conduct interview with such a user.
- 3) Participants have to be involved into at least one active PM use case implemented within organization. As described below, we asked participants to choose a specific use case for answering questions. Therefore, when a user had no use cases at the moment, we decided to not conduct interview with such a user.

For this study we on purpose did not invite PM consultants or developers and analysts from 3rd parties (consultancy, vendors, service providers), as we expect that they mostly have PM output **producers** role. We refer to data engineers and analysts as PM output **producers**, and to end business users as PM output **consumers**. Therefore, we expect that end consumers are less involved in the technical development—and therefore less knowledgeable about the processing that has been made on the input data— but still essential to understanding the final output and responsible for identifying and realizing the value out of PM use.

2. Participants Overview

The table contains the overview of 18 users (**u**) that participated in the study. It highlights the user's role with respect to PM (**Role**), region, where user performs PM activities (**PM Activities Location**), PM experience in years (**Years of PM Experience**), the approximate number of different PM projects and/or PM use cases within one project that users have experience with (**PM Projects/Use Cases**), **PM solution** that users are currently using within their organization (if they have an individual experience with many solutions, we ask them to pick one that they currently use), the frequency of the PM solution use (chosen from daily, weekly, monthly, other).

User/Participant Code	Role	PM Activities Location	Years of PM Experience	PM Projects/Use Cases	PM Solution	How often use PM
U#1	Project Sponsor	Global	3	>10	Celonis	Daily
U#2	Process Excellence Specialist	Global	8	>10	Celonis	Daily
U#3	Business Analyst	EU	1	1-5	Celonis	Daily
U#4	Process Excellence Specialist	Global	2	5-10	Celonis	Daily
U#5	Other: Data Analyst	EU	1	1-5	Disco	Monthly
U#6	Business Analyst	EU	1,5	5-10	Celonis	Weekly
U#7	Other: Subject Matter Expert	EU	1,5	1-5	Celonis	Daily
U#8	Process Excellence Specialist	APAC	5	5-10	Celonis	Monthly
U#9	Process Excellence Specialist	EU	2	1-5	Celonis	Weekly
U#10	Program Manager	Global	1	>10	Celonis	Daily
U#11	Process Excellence Specialist	EU	3	5-10	Celonis	Weekly
U#12	Business Analyst	EU	4	1-5	Celonis	Weekly
U#13	Process Excellence Specialist	Global	4	>10	QPR Process Analyzer	Daily
U#14	Process Mining Lead	EU	3	>10	Microsoft Process Mining	Daily
U#15	Business Engagement Manager	EU	3	1-5	Celonis	Weekly
U#16	Process Owner	Global	3	>10	Celonis	Daily
U#17	Business Analyst	Global	6 months	>10	Celonis	Daily
U#18	Process Team Lead and PM Key User	EU	3	5-10	Celonis	Daily

3. Use Case Selection Criteria

For answering questions, we asked users to choose and focus on their own process mining **use case** implemented within the organization. By use case we refer to the set of analytics in the PM solution, for example, set of dashboards/visuals in the PM solution for analyzing order cancellations in Order-to-Cash process. This way we could get their answers based on a real-life example. We believe to improve the understanding of trust of PM users in PM input and output, we should focus on investigating real-life work settings of PM users.

We did not provide any strict requirements for the use case selection. In case a user is involved into multiple use cases, we discussed which one to choose and decided to focus on the one that users use more often. By focusing on the most frequently used use case, we ensured that users engaged with a use case they know well and, as such, have developed a good understanding of their trust over repeated interactions.

*For the anonymization purpose, we do not share the detailed information about the use cases, as there are some use cases that we consider rather unique.

4. Interview (Survey) Details

The interview protocol can be found below.

Part I

General Information about Process Mining Experience

3. What is your current role with respect to Process Mining?

- Business Analyst
- Process Excellence Specialist
- Process Owner
- Other

4. Where do you currently conduct your Process Mining activities (please choose the region)?

<https://help.adjust.com/en/article/countries-by-region>

- EMEA - Benelux (Belgium, Luxembourg, the Netherlands)
- EMEA - UK/Ireland
- DACH (Germany, Austria, Switzerland)
- EMEA - Other (not Benelux, not part of DACH, not UK/Ireland)
- Scandinavia (Denmark, Norway, Sweden)
- LATAM (Latin America)
- APAC (Asia-Pacific)
- NA (North America)
- Other

5. How many years of Process Mining Experience do you have?

Feel free to provide approx. number

Enter your answer

6. How many Process Mining Projects/Use cases do you have experience with? (feel free to provide approximate number/range)

Feel free to provide approx. number or range. For example: 5-10

Enter your answer

7. Which Process Mining Solution(s) you have experience with?

If multiple, please select one you currently/recently use

Celonis

Disco

UiPath Process Mining

Microsoft Process Mining

Process Mining by Software AG

Other

8. How often do you use Process Mining solution?

Hourly

Daily

Weekly

Monthly

Other

9. Which Process you are currently working on (in Process Mining solution)?

Please select one or multiple options below or specify in Other

Order-to-Cash

Purchase-to-Pay

Plant Maintenance

Other

10. Which Use Case/Analysis you are currently working on (in Process Mining solution)?

Please select one or multiple options below or specify in Other

Time-To-Deliver

Shipped Not Invoiced

On-Time-In-Full

Automation Ratio

Open Invoices

3-way-Match

Other

Part II

Questions related to the **Trust** to Process Mining Analysis and Results

11. Use Case Focus for the next Questions

The questions in **Part II** and **Part III** are better asked based on a **dashboard/analysis** you are currently using in Process Mining solution.

You are kindly requested to open one of your Process Mining analyses (do not share it, just open it and see for yourself) and use it when answering the questions. If you have multiple dashboards, you are free to choose one (however, the advice is to open the one you use the most **often**).

Share the high-level description of the analysis/use case you have opened:

Enter your answer

12. For how long do you use this use case?

Less than a month

1-6 months

6 months - 1 year

more than 1 year

Other

13. How often do you have a data refresh for this use case?

How often the delta data is uploaded

Daily

Weekly

Monthly

Other

14. How would you rate overall input data/output results trust? Please choose one of the options below

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree or Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
I feel that I can trust data quality overall and data that was used for building PM analysis	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I feel that results of PM analysis are accurate and reliable	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

15. If you replied to one or more questions not Strongly Agree, can you please share some details why?

Enter your answer

16. Freshness

For the chosen use case/overview, is it possible for you to clearly see and know when was the latest data refresh?

- Yes, I can see it in the overview
- No, but I know where to check it
- No, but I trust that the data is the freshest
- No, I cannot be always sure if the data is freshest
- Other

17. Accuracy

How can you verify the accuracy of the data shown? How do you usually perform such a check (if perform)?

Enter your answer

18. Completeness

How can you verify that the data/results provided are complete? (e.g. no records, no documents)

Enter your answer

19. Do you perform accuracy and completeness checks often?

Only during the initial implementation

Regularly after implementation

From time-to-time (not regularly)

Never

Other

20. Reliability

Do you feel comfortable using Process Mining results in reports or sharing them with stakeholders (e.g. sending an e-mail based on Process Mining results to a supplier/customer)?

Yes, I am already doing it (for example, downloading report from Process Mining solution and share it with others/third parties)

Yes, I do not do this yet, but planning to do

No, I have to double check the data and perform extra manipulations before sharing it

No, I cannot use it at all

Other

5. Coding Scheme

The following table contains the final coding scheme. It has information regarding the high-level theme the code is assigned to, statement example and user identifier (#U). Per each category there are number of users mentioned it per input/output and rating. More detailed coding can be found in other supplementary materials.

Theme	Category	Code	Focused Coding	Statement Examples	# High (Strongly Agree)	# Medium (Agree)	# Low (Other)	Frequency Input	Frequency Output	# Users
Overall Trust	Trust in Input and Output	OT1	Relying on personal previous experience and/or validations	#U6: I was not a part of the initial project [of this use case implementation]. So, I can say Agree but this is because I had to perform a lot of my own explorations and my own validations. #U9: I would say Agree, that has the reason that I am involved into the validation and customization. #U16: I am new user and this report is already built.	6	9		7	8	8
		OT2	Relying on colleagues experience and/or validations	#U1: I trust that my colleagues performed sufficient number of tests and quality checks. #U3: There are many users, myself and my colleagues who are involved into this dashboard. I expect that if something is wrong, then other users will also indicate this and mention.	6	3		4	5	5
		OT3	Being aware of known issues (with input data, with Process Mining solution)	#U3: We see that the raw data is not correct, in ERP system itself #U13: We did not go into the specific analyses. As we know that the data is not accurate. #U14: Because there are still some bugs in the tool from [Vendor] and due to the bugs, you cannot rely on the data. #U17: because we are still somehow having cases, I guess it is because of our definition, and making the link with the data available.	5			3	2	5
		OT4	Accepting risk of possible issues	#U1: There could be sometimes "false-alarms" #U5: I know that there are sometimes issues and we can never come to 100%, you never know #U9: We are also facing the risk, that we are sharing the information that is incorrect...we approve this risk	5	5		4	6	6
		OT5	Blind Trust (rely on PM solution, due to the role with respect to PM)	#U4: One of my job responsibilities is also about convincing others to trust the data #U5: I rely on [name of Process Mining solution], because we do not develop a lot of things on top		8	1	4	5	6
		OT6	Experiencing difficulty to perform validation (customizations in the source system, complexity of the output, not enough knowledge about the input)	#U14: I know that the data are 100% correct. I quite often struggle to understand what they mean, to interpret it #U8: There are still some issues. It is, let's say 5%, but then it is not 100%. Problem is that we have a lot of customized things #U9: some variables that are determined by [name of PM solution] logic and for this I do not know the exact input	2	2		2	2	2
		OT7	Regular and/or massive use without major issues	#U10: So far, we have not find any missing cases. #U15: At the beginning was different and now it is stable. #U18: This is my daily job and I am seeing stuff that if that would not be in the dashboard, it would be missed		8	4	6	6	6

For example (see screenshot below), for **OT1 there were** 8 unique users, who mentioned personal previous experience and validations (u3, u6, u7, u9, u10, u14, u15, u16). Seven users mentioned it for input and output (IO) and 1 more user mentioned it only for the output. It was mentioned 6 times for High rating by 3 users (3 times for High rating for the output and 3 times for the High rating for the input) and 9 times for Medium rating by 5 users (5 times for the output and 4 times for the input).

Codes
 U1
 U2
 U3
 U4
 U5
 U6
 U7
 U8
 U9
 U10
 U11
 U12
 U13
 U14
 U15
 U16
 U17
 U18

C5 - (Limited but Sufficient) Trust: rely on previous and/or personal validation experience
 C13 - (High) Trust: rely on previous and/or personal validation experience